

Figure S1. Map of intertidal collecting locations. Each white dot shows a location where sponges were collected from habitat and pools exposed at low tide. Boxes outline regions shown in figures S2 and S3.

Figure S2. Map of subtidal collecting locations in Southern California. Each dot shows a location where sponges were collected using SCUBA. Black dots show where the most common species (*Drasmodon mexicanum*) was found, and white dots show where it was not found.

Figure S3. Map of subtidal collecting locations in Central California. Each dot shows a location where sponges were collected using SCUBA. Black dots show where the most common species (*Dragmacdon mexicanum*) was found, and white dots show where it was not found.

